

QUEENSLAND UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY

Faculty of Education

Master of Education Thesis

Values-based Education in Schools in the 2000s: The Australian Experience

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(June, 2010)

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Abstract

This thesis explores the teaching of values in Australian schools through a framework established by the Australian Federal government during the 2000s. This paper focuses on: the approaches employed by the Australian Federal government in the implementation of Values Education; and the application of cases of values-based education utilized by school cluster groups throughout Australia. This research explores the implementation of a values-based education program on a national scale and provides recommendations on: best practices for teaching values-based education in schools; and the inclusion of key stakeholders, such as, school administrators & staff, teachers, students, parents, and members of the wider community in order to achieve the successful establishment of a wide scale approach to the teaching of values in schools.

Keywords

Cases, discourses, moral development, policy, restorative practices, service learning, social action, social skills, teacher efficacy, values

Introduction

Bajovic, Rizzo and Engemann (2009, p. 3) proffer a definition of character as “a complex set of psychological characteristics, formed in part by growth in cognition that enables a person to act as a moral agent”. From this definition, character and morality are deemed to be interrelated. Thus, character can be considered, at least in part, to be dependent on moral development as this dependent association provides the founding definition of character for the intensive purpose of this explorative report. Subsequently, character education can be considered to involve the construction of moral knowledge and social reasoning. Character education in schools is therefore an educational construct from which students learn morally and socially acceptable behavior.

Common labels such as character education, moral education and values-based education are used by educationalists to describe the teaching of behavior, attitudes and ideals that are appropriate for individual and group interactions in a societal context. The term character education is used in the introduction because it is widely used in educational practice and research around the world and while moral education is also a commonly used term, it is values-based education that is the preferred term for this paper because it is prominently used in Australia. The aforementioned definition of character, by Bajovic, Rizzo and Engemann (2009), will hold and be considered to include key traits that are intrinsic to values-based education.

Students learn social and moral behavior in schools, at home and in the wider community. In countries around the world, values-based education and its application in schools has been discussed at the governmental level and implemented at the school level. Examples include: the United Kingdom's government supported voluntary programme – S.E.A.L. – Social and Emotional Aspects of Learning; C.A.S.E.L. – Collaborative for Academic, Social and Emotional Learning in the U.S.A.; C.E.P.N.Z. – Character Education Programmes of New Zealand in N.Z. and the Australian Federal government's sanctioned and funded Values Education Program.

This paper explores the implementation of values-based education in schools, with particular focus given to the Australian primary school context. Theoretical and empirical evidence is used to support the inclusion of values-based education in Australian primary schools in order to demonstrate the validity and reliability of successful strategies implemented by schools and communities for teaching and supporting students' moral development, namely: improving student learning opportunities; and fostering harmonious student relations and supporting productive attitudes among students toward their peers and others, in general. In a broader Australian context, this paper explores the policy approaches used to support values-based education in Australian schools, with emphasis given to the inclusion of values-based education in curricula. Research established in this paper is of benefit to practicing pre-service and in-service teachers and offers key school stakeholders in the school community a deeper understanding of what values-based education is and how it can be implemented in teaching and learning at schools and, to some extent, at home. Research findings in this area of education provide the opportunity for teachers to improve: their professional practice and modeling of

appropriate classroom values-based activities; and their ability to include parents and other key stakeholders in the character development of students.

The Significance of Values-based Education in Society

The significance of values-based education both in our society and our schools cannot be emphasized enough and this sentiment is marked in the thoughts of former United Nations Secretary-General (1997-2007), Koffi Annan, who said:

“Values are not there to help philosophers or theologians, but to help people live their lives and organize their societies...and we need to find within ourselves the will to live by the values we proclaim, in our private lives, in our local and national societies, and in the world” (Coad, 2007, p. 1).

In this context, it can be seen that values-based education is a universal undertaking. The significance of teaching values in schools has not been lost on Australian policy makers and educators.

Synopses of Several Fundamental Theory-based Educational Approaches to Values-based Education Discourses

Brady (2008) observes that each of the following commonly used theoretical approaches to values-based education have different methodologies and that they defy a universal teaching model. Later in this paper, school cluster programs utilizing values-based education through a variety of teaching and learning strategies will be evidenced. Teachers can benefit from understanding how to use these apparently disparate approaches and integrate them into their own models of teaching and learning, and particularly so in the case of values-based education. A brief synopsis of each of these educational approaches is outlined hereafter.

Inculcation is defined as “to teach and impress by frequent repetitions or admonitions” (Merriam Webster Online Dictionary and Thesaurus). Proponents of this approach recognize values as being socially and/or culturally acceptable behavior that students take on and adopt into their own value systems. During the inculcation process of teaching and learning character, students are addressed as reactors rather than initiators of values and learn that certain values are absolute and universal (Huitt, 2004). Inculcation discourses include, but not exclusively:

modeling; positive and negative reinforcement; manipulating alternatives; games and simulations; and role playing, see Appendix 2.

Advocates of moral development observe moral thinking as developing in stages through a specific sequence. Kohlberg's six stages approach presents the primary focus of moral developmental progress, see Appendix 1. Kohlberg's Stages of Moral Development model operates on the assumption that individuals, that is, students, unvaryingly progress developmentally in their moral thinking and that exposure to the next higher level is essential to advancing their moral development (Huitt, 2004). Real-life examples of student responses in a level by level explanation might include (Beach, 1975):

1. Pre-conventional level

Stage 1: Punishment/Obedience orientation – avoiding punishment;

Stage 2: Instrumental/Relativist orientation – doing what you need to get what you want;

2. Conventional level

Stage 3: Interpersonal Concordance orientation – getting along with the values of your own group;

Stage 4: Authority and Social Order Maintaining orientation – following all the rules of the society; and

3. Post-conventional or Principled level

Stage 5: Social Contract Legalistic orientation - seeing laws (rules) and agreements that lead to the greatest good; and

Stage 6: Universal Ethical Principle orientation - understanding principles behind the systems of laws (rules).

Students are viewed as active initiators and reactors within the context of their environments and although the environment can determine the content of one's experiences, it cannot determine its form (Huitt, 2004). Moral development discourses include, but not exclusively: moral dilemma episodes with small-group discussion; and relatively structured and argumentative without necessarily coming to what may be termed as a right answer, see Appendix 2.

The analysis approach promotes the use of logical thinking and scientific investigation in dealing with values issues. The foundation of this approach rests with the assumption that valuing is the cognitive process of determining and justifying facts and beliefs derived from those facts (Huitt, 2004). Analysis approach discourses include, but not exclusively: structured rational discussion that demands application of reasons as well as evidence; testing principles; analyzing analogous cases; library research; field research; and debate, see Appendix 2.

Values clarification focuses on helping students to use both rational thinking and emotional awareness to examine personal behavior patterns, as well as clarifying and actualizing their values. Through self-actualization, that is, realizing one's own maximum potential and possibilities, students freely choose from alternatives, reflecting on the consequences of those alternatives and acting upon their own choices (Huitt, 2004). Students are viewed as initiators within their society and environment and are encouraged by educators to change their environment to meet their needs. Values clarification discourses include, but not exclusively: role-playing games; simulations; contrived or real value-laden situations; in-depth self-analysis exercises; sensitivity activities; out-of-class activities; and small group discussions, see Appendix 2.

Action learning emphasizes community-based rather than classroom-based learning experiences. Advocates of this approach stress the need to provide specific opportunities for learners to act on their values (Huitt, 2004). The learner moves beyond thinking and feeling to acting. Values are identified from the interaction of the individual and the society rather than solely on the society or the individual. Action learning discourses include, but not exclusively: methods listed for analysis and values clarification; projects within school and community practice; skill practice in group organizing and interpersonal relations, see Appendix 2.

While various educational discourses have been and continue to be employed in Australian values-based education programs in Australian schools, the Australian Values Education Schools Good Practices trials 2005/06 revealed the extent of usage of the above-mentioned discourse types. In Appendix 12, the occurrence of each of these discourse types in programs implemented in the Values Education Good Practices Schools trial, Stage 1, is outlined and rated numerically.

A study by Jones (2009) using the National Framework for Values Education in Australian Schools (N.F.V.E.A.S.) as the primary source of data collection, found that among 102 schools in the Stage 1 trial, and among 16 different discourse types used in values-based education, two of the top three choices used by schools included values inculcation and social action, that is, action learning. An exploration of the Stage 1 outcomes follows later in this paper.

Australian Government Policy Initiatives on Values-based Education

Australia had not been subjected to such an intense campaign of values-based education in its history prior to the emergence of the National Framework for Values Education in Australian Schools (N.F.V.E.A.S.). In the past century, values-based education materialized most overtly and explicitly in the religious models of independent schools, whereas distinct values education from a state schools perspective has been largely neglected and incorporated in some form as a component of other studies, such as social, physical or civics education (Jones, 2009).

The N.F.V.E.A.S. is a national framework agreed to and endorsed by all of the State and Territory Ministers of Education and was distributed to all Australian schools in 2005. The Australian Government Department of Education, Employment and Workplace Relations website (www.curriculum.edu.au/values) outlines the vision of the Framework for use in all Australian schools and states that values education be included in a planned and systematic way by:

- *articulating, in consultation with their school community, the school's mission ethos;*
- *developing student responsibility in local, national and global contexts and building student resilience and social skills;*
- *ensuring values are incorporated into school policies and teaching programs across the key learning areas; and*
- *reviewing the outcomes of their values education practices.*

Beyond this outlined vision, the N.F.V.E.A.S. represents a comprehensive and demonstrable instrument of commitment by the Australian Federal and State governments, school administrators, teachers, parents and the wider community to support the values development of Australian school children in the sense of how children acquire their values and how they make sense of them. In 1999, before this national framework had been established, the

National Goals for Schooling in the Twenty-First Century reflected the significance placed upon values-based education by the Australian government when all State and Territory Education Ministers signed the Adelaide Declaration stating that:

“Australia’s future depends on each citizen having the necessary knowledge, understanding, skills and values for a productive and rewarding life in an educated, just and open society. High quality schooling is central to achieving this vision...Schooling provides a foundation for young Australian’s intellectual, physical, social, moral, spiritual and aesthetic development” (Australian Government: Department of Education, Employment and Workplace Relations, 2005).

In the National Framework document of 2005 (Australian Government: Department of Education, Employment and Workplace Relations), two significant observations stand out: Firstly, schools that participated in this study demonstrated a desire to participate in values-based education to support the character development of their students; and secondly, those schools that took part in the study appeared to emphasize the need for partnerships with parents/caregivers and their local community. Referenced in Appendix 3, an outcome of the N.F.V.E.A.S., 2005, nine values are identified for values education in Australian schools: care and compassion; doing your best; fair go; freedom, honesty & trustworthiness; integrity; respect; responsibility; and understanding & tolerance.

In 2005, all schools across Australia were invited to apply for Commonwealth funding, forming school clusters of between four to ten schools, designing projects that would be chosen for the implementation of local school community based programs by the Australian Commonwealth government under guidelines established in the N.F.V.E.A.S., 2005. The successful school cluster groups were awarded commonwealth funding grants ranging from \$45,000 to \$100,000 as a result of a competitive selection process (Australian Government: Department of Education, Employment and Workplace Relations, 2005). The successful inclusion of values-based education in school curriculum is supported in the case study projects that follow in the next two sections of this paper, that is, Stage 1 (2005/06) and Stage 2 (2008) of the Final Report of the Values Education Good Practices Schools Project (V.E.G.P.S.P.). These projects were primarily bottom-up in their nature and not intended to research any top-down approach or theory of values-based education (Australian Government: Department of Education, Employment and Workplace Relations, 2008). The Australian Commonwealth government has continued to build on the success of Stages 1 & 2 and in 2008/09 it has funded

the Values in Action Schools Project (V.A.S.P.), demonstrating its ongoing commitment to the design, implementation and evaluation of values-based education in Australian schools using a cross-curricular approach in many cases.

Nine Australian Values of the National Framework for Values Education in Australian Schools

The growth of civics and citizenship education, that is, the teaching and learning of students to work together and take practical action together to become responsible citizens and positive contributors to society, was triggered in Australia by the quest to define the national character in the lead up to the 2001 centenary of federation (Clark, 2008). The makeup of the Australian character that was decided upon and promoted by the Commonwealth government in 2005, is depicted in the superimposed image of the iconic, heroic and exemplary Anzac figure from World War One, John Simpson Kirkpatrick, see Appendix 3, who is leading his donkey which is laden with a wounded man. Simpson was an Anzac stretcher bearer who rescued wounded soldiers from the battlefield of Gallipoli and who lost his own life while volunteering this service on the battlefield. The Education minister (in 2005), Brendan Nelson, stated that John Simpson Kirkpatrick symbolically represented everything that is at the heart of what it means to be an Australian (Clark, 2008). On the Australian Character oriented values poster, see Appendix 3, the values of which are frequently referred to in the N.F.V.E.A.S. case study projects explored later in this paper, are the nine central values of this common values approach, mandated by the Commonwealth government, to be learned about and practiced in all Australian schools. Below, they are listed and brief definitions of scope are offered for each of them:

- ***Care and Compassion:*** *care for self and others;*
- ***Doing Your Best:*** *seek to accomplish something worthy and admirable, try hard, pursue excellence;*
- ***Fair Go:*** *(a particularly Australian ideal!): pursue and protect the common good where all people are treated fairly for a just society;*
- ***Freedom:*** *enjoy the rights and privileges of being an Australian citizen, free from unnecessary interference or control, and stand up for the rights of others;*
- ***Honesty and Trustworthiness:*** *be honest, sincere and seek the truth;*
- ***Integrity:*** *act in accordance with principles of moral and ethical conduct, ensure*

consistency between words and deeds;

- **Respect:** *treat others with consideration and regard, respect another person's point of view;*
- **Responsibility:** *be accountable for one's own actions, resolve differences in constructive, non-violent and peaceful ways contribute to society and to civic life, take care of the environment; and*
- **Understanding, Tolerance and Inclusion:** *be aware of others and their cultures, accept diversity within a democratic society, being included and including others.*

Clark (2008) notes that the use of the iconic Australian image of Simpson Kirkpatrick and his donkey is a well-received choice, however, to use it exclusively as a primary promotional tool in Australian schools runs the risk of reducing the sentiment of the *National Framework* to a restrictive form of nationalism that does not necessarily accommodate the diversity of views within anyone classroom, school or within Australia. Richardson (2005) contends that values should look to capture both the traditions and spirit of a society but also provide vision.

Implementing the National Framework for Values Education in Australian Schools Report for the Values Education Good Practices Schools Project - Stage 1, Final Report, 2006

The V.E.G.P.S.P. - Stage 1 (Australian Government: Department of Education, Employment and Workplace Relations, 2005), aimed to identify and exemplify good practices in so that Australian schools could implement values-based education as an integral part of schooling teaching and learning in a planned and systematic way. Twenty-six selected school clusters including 166 schools, consisting of 70.000 students, participated in this project using their own contexts, implementing various values-based education projects and presenting evidence, that is, school experiences and reports on aspects of school life, for example, student learning, student behaviors, teacher professional practice relationships in schools and school culture change. The Final Report of Stage 1 of this project was completed in 2006, Stage 2 ensued and its Final Report was completed in 2008. The following set of principles was established from the collective conclusions drawn from cluster groups that participated in Stage 1 of this project (Australian Government: Department of Education, Employment and Workplace Relations, 2006):

1. *It is essential to reach agreement in the school community about the values that guide the school and the language in which they are described;*
2. *Values education is sustained over time only through a whole school approach that engages all sectors of the school community;*
3. *School leadership is critical in developing values education as a core part of schooling;*
4. *Values must be explicitly articulated and explicitly taught;*
5. *It is critical to student learning that there is consistency and congruence between the values espoused and the values modeled;*
6. *Professional learning of all teachers is critical at all stages of the development of values education;*
7. *Developing positive relationships in classrooms and schools is central to values education;*
8. *Success is achieved when values education is integral to all aspects of school life;*
9. *Schools working in clusters can foster effective professional development and quality teaching and learning as well as provide support for values education initiatives; and*
10. *Supportive critical friends and mentors contribute markedly to professional development and the values education work of schools.*

The cluster group case studies presented in this paper were selected because they mainly consisted of primary schools and they used values-based education in diversely different ways. School clusters used action research to improve values-based education, for example, accounts of teacher experiences by way of case writing; student records of achievement, class attendance in their case study and the development of the teachers' work on values-based education. Action research, in an educational context, is a form of staff development focusing on inquiry of a participant's own practice, essentially involving the pursuit of finding solutions to classroom problems, in a scientific and situation specific way (Arthur-Kelly, Lyons, Butterfield, & Gordon, 2006). The use of action research in the V.E.G.P.S.P. was enhanced by the implementation of the Australian-based University Associates Network (U.A.N.) which comprised of mainly education faculty deans and professors, who provided assistance with school level action research and offered advice on values-based education, professional development and the process of case

study writing (Australian Government: Department of Education, Employment and Workplace Relations, 2005).

Australian Schools School Cluster Case Studies: Values-based Education Implementation (1)

Case 1: A Restorative Practices Approach Taking Small Steps Towards the Big Picture of Emotional Literacy - Calwell Cluster (Australian Capital Territory)

The focus of the Calwell Schools Cluster project, comprising 5 schools, was to improve the capacity of parents, students and teachers to engage in restorative practices in school and community relationships. It was imperative for the restorative practices approach to use values that reflected the school the community at large because support of the whole school community was required for the project to succeed. Despite initial cynicism from some teachers, clear explanations from school administrators about this project and their messages that it was to make teachers' work easier rather than be an additional burden allayed concerns and initial resistance that might have existed (Australian Government: Department of Education, Employment and Workplace Relations, 2006). Through a 'values' audit, each school conducted information gathering techniques to formalize a list of values for Doing Your Best, for example, using written or phone surveys with parents, community forums and teacher and student discussion groups, to achieve this initial goal. The outcome of this research is evidenced in Appendix 5. Additionally, in both this initial stage of project development and during classroom activity implementation process, cooperative discussion strategy tools, for example, Y-charts and Placemats, see Appendix 13, aided this process successfully (Australian Government: Department of Education, Employment and Workplace Relations, 2006). In relation to cooperative learning structures, the *Y-Chart* is a tool for discussing a multi-faceted issue and can be used to brainstorm what a topic looks like, feels like and sounds like; and a *Placemat* is a tool for encouraging students to record, share their ideas around a key idea or issue (Kiernan, 2005).

Schools in this cluster used the list of values, aforementioned and illustrated in Appendix 5, as their basis for the development of emotional literacy, which formed the core of the project classroom lessons. Communications for sharing project information among and within schools

and the community took place through newsletters, media, public events such as Harmony Day, staff/parent/citizen meetings, websites, school assemblies, etc. The curriculum package was finally developed after approximately one month of individual teacher research among school cluster members. By trialing lessons in their own classrooms, members of the writing team revised them with the additional support of feedback from other teachers. This process of revision and feedback was required because consensus among all teachers would be needed before these lessons would be taught in Term 1, 2006 (Australian Government: Department of Education, Employment and Workplace Relations, 2006). Critical to the success of the implementation of the emotional literacy lessons was that professional development needed to be continual so that staff would become familiar with the lessons and their format and the range of different ways in which they can be used and this is particularly important when school staff leave and new staff arrive so that program continuity in the classroom is not disrupted (Australian Government: Department of Education, Employment and Workplace Relations, 2005). The attention paid to professional development in the case of this cluster group resulted in 98% of staff involved indicating that they were very positive about the curriculum package and felt very motivated about delivering the lessons to their students (Australian Government: Department of Education, Employment and Workplace Relations, 2005). Appendix 6 illustrates a sample lesson used by Year 7 students to learn about acceptable social behaviors, cooperation and responsibility. At the end of the 120 lesson curriculum, Calwell Cluster school teachers demonstrated their proactive support for this project and the specific experience of one of the teachers sums up the success of this values-based education project (Australian Government: Department of Education, Employment and Workplace Relations, 2005):

“...not only in explicit social and emotional lessons taught, but the transference of these skills is becoming apparent...in a Years 1-2 classroom, when a young girl came in from lunch saying, “I’m sad because (student) would not play with me...” Before the teacher had a chance to speak with the girls, another Year 1 girl initiated the use of relational questioning to assist her peers to solve their problem and hence feel happy once again with each other and within their friendship.”

*Case 2: A Philosophical Approach Philosophy in the Classroom - Gold Coast North Cluster
(Queensland)*

Comprising four schools, the Gold Coast Cluster sought to explore and engage the philosophical and ethical aspects of the curriculum in order to link with the National Framework and create a school ethos where students have the capacity to exercise judgment and responsibility in matters of morality, ethics and social justice, and the capacity to make informed decisions about their lives (Australian Government: Department of Education, Employment and Workplace Relations, 2005). The facilitation of a community of inquiry underpinned the pedagogical approach to the inclusion of philosophy in the cluster's curriculum. The program aimed at guiding students to work together, generate and answer questions about curriculum based philosophical issues with critical, creative, collaborative and caring inquiry (Australian Government: Department of Education, Employment and Workplace Relations, 2005). Schools within this cluster accepted the whole school approach for the inclusion of philosophy in their curriculum and this required the implementation of substantial professional development (P.D.) and ongoing support before the project could be introduced in classroom teaching and learning. A large arrangement of shared activities including the review of school values and purpose statements, the usual rounds of meetings and discussions with parents and students, as mentioned in Case 1, complemented P.D. (Australian Government: Department of Education, Employment and Workplace Relations, 2005). A specific initiative that proved successful with students was the implementation of a V9 vouchers system, reflecting the nine values of Australian schooling, see Appendix 3. The V9 voucher system recognized and encouraged the enacting of positive values and the rewards were awarded certificates in class or in the playground when students demonstrated any of the nine values depicted in the National Framework for Values Education in Australian Schools document (2005) that are listed on the teaching aid poster exhibited in Appendix 3. Classroom activities utilized in the implementation of this project focused on students learning through a community of inquiry approach, an example of which is illustrated in this brief recollection of one teacher who talks about what the students did:

"...sit in a circle, learn to respect, listen to and understand a diverse range of views...philosophical exploration...encourages students to take increased responsibility for their own learning processes...think for themselves...develop higher order thinking skills in the context of meaningful discussion" (Australian Government: Department of Education, Employment and Workplace Relations, 2006).

Higher order thinking skills development is evidenced in the non-topic specific question techniques explored in Appendix 7 and specific question examples also used in cluster activities, such as:

- *How should we treat our friends?*
- *Should we always think for ourselves?*
- *What does giving someone a “fair go” mean?*

Among the schools of this cluster, a typical class lesson using the community of inquiry approach to values-based education involved a group reading a source text subsequently followed by the generating of agenda specific discussion questions and collaborative inquiry by students in the class. The use of a *Plus, Minus, Interesting* (P.M.I.) organizer enhanced this process, see Appendix 14. The P.M.I. organizer is a lateral and creative thinking tool and it is used for affective processing to consider the pluses, minuses and interesting points felt about a lesson, concept or issue (Kiernan, 2005). Philosophical inquiry led discussions involved the following key elements (Australian Government: Department of Education, Employment and Workplace Relations, 2006):

- *The best answer is not provided or validated by the teacher;*
- *The class has the responsibility for both constructing and evaluating the range of possible responses to a question;*
- *Even if some answers are difficult to come by, some answers can reasonably be judged better, more defensible, than others;*
- *Students can share ideas and must consider many different perspectives; and*
- *Participation in the community of inquiry is primarily oral so that they (students) can offer their opinions in an atmosphere of care and safety where they can try out ideas with the guarantee that they will be listened to.*

The concept of the community of inquiry that took place in classroom exchanges between students and teachers increased levels of respect within both class groups and the school community, improved student learning and created calmer school environments (Australian Government: Department of Education, Employment and Workplace Relations, 2005).

Case 3: A Social Action Approach Teaching for Social Action - Nerang Alliance of State Schools Cluster (Queensland)

The Nerang Alliance of State Schools Cluster was an association of seven schools and a Queensland state government environmental education center. The main focus of this cluster's project was the use social literacy to inculcate values-based education in all key learning areas using Social Action as an instrumental tool in this educational approach. Notably, in the initial stages of the project, despite difficulties with deciding how a common approach to values-based social literacy could be achieved, the requirement of releasing personal egos and individual school identities was necessary for full support to be given (Department of Education, Employment and Workplace Relations, 2006). In Appendix 8, this cluster demonstrates how it uses values/inquiry based learning in the context of social action literacy across mixed age primary school levels. The values social literacy units listed in Appendix 8 represent a commitment from the cluster schools to integrate values-based education across more than one key learning area during the curriculum's development and implementation, for example, Studies of Society and the Environment (S.O.S.E.) & Science; S.O.S.E., Health and Physical Education & Arts. In Appendix 9, the 'What does it mean to be water wise?' unit exhibits the teachers' efforts to encourage direct action from students involved in this project to move beyond the scope of their school learning to engage in this inquiry based learning process.

A key challenge for the success of teachers participating in this project was negotiating social actions and supporting the education process to achieve the goal of encouraging students to have confidence in their work to the point that they believed that they had achieved these social actions themselves (Australian Government: Department of Education, Employment and Workplace Relations, 2006). To effectively prepare students for this educational learning experience, cluster teachers who developed the Water Wise program activity recommended the use K-W-L (Know–Want–Learn) strategy, to help students to construct meaning before, during and after the activity. Appendix 15 exhibits an example of a K-W-L worksheet. Additionally, teachers were aware of the overcrowded curriculum that existed and their need to work smarter rather than harder to incorporate values-based education into their teaching and learning outcomes. In Appendix 16, a Venn diagram tool exemplifies how Australian values and social

literacy was combined successfully to implement a Social Action project. Finally, the teachers' efforts to give students explicit exposure to the nine core values, see Appendix 3, contributed significantly to the use of a common language and the promotion of values awareness in a successful school approach to values-based education as noted by one teacher (Australian Government: Department of Education, Employment and Workplace Relations, 2006):

"It was fascinating to see students use appropriate vocabulary when they recognized the word values in questions (and discussions)...the Values Based Unit that I taught...indeed made an impact on the students."

Case 4: A Service Learning Approach Taking values to the community - Red Earth Community Cluster (Victoria)

The Red Earth Community Cluster determined as its main objective - to develop practicing values in community settings with student groups engaging in community service in a variety of ways. Several of the project activities included (Australian Government: Department of Education, Employment and Workplace Relations, 2006):

- *Year 6 students creating a patchwork knitted rug and visiting the residents of a local aged care home to present it and sing carols with the residents, while Year 3 & 4 regularly visited them to play games; and*
- *Year 3 & 4 students created a sensory garden at a local day center with the support of a national hardware retailer.*

Through these action projects, the cluster teachers sought to instill the ideal of Respect as the foremost value to be reflected upon. In Appendix 10, the list of behaviors that support Respect is exemplified in the thoughts and words of students who partook in this values-based education program. The cluster teachers' efforts to engage parents in their program resulted in mixed success. Contrasting examples support the contention that clear foci need to be established before program activities take place. While a well-publicized teacher-parent values-based education presentation night drew little support from parents, a parent-student night and the attendance of a local sports star, as a key guest speaker, attracted a large attendance and very positive comments about the evening program (Australian Government: Department of Education, Employment and Workplace Relations, 2006).

Students, with the support of teachers, the wider school community, parents and society, in recognizing that they have the power to shape and influence decision-making in their school and greater community, is a powerful and effective way to engage them in school life and educative processes (Coad, 2007). The Red Earth Cluster exemplified the efforts of teachers and the school community to support students in their values based learning outcomes. The above documented four case studies testify to the benefits of student inclusion and interaction in teaching and learning outcomes where values based education is involved.

Implementing the National Framework for Values Education in Australian Schools Report for the Values Education Good Practices Schools Project - Stage 2, Final Report, 2008

The most effective strategies for improving values-based education researched from Stage 1 were adopted or modified in the next stage of the final report project. Stage 2 operated from 2006 to 2008, comprising 143 schools among 25 school clusters, building on and expanding the developments from Stage 1 within other school contexts, namely through the demonstration of good practices for implementing values-based education. Evidence of how values based education was incorporated into school curriculums has been clearly reviewed in the previous section of this investigative report, that is, Stage 1. Although extensive case studies are demonstrated in Stage 2 of this Commonwealth funded project, the outcomes of Stage 1 & 2 cluster school case study projects were similar. However, strengths and weaknesses were again highlighted in Stage 2 of the Final Report and fundamental educational practices were refined and succinctly defined in 10 good practices. These were identified at the end of V.E.G.P.S.P. - Stage 2 (Australian Government: Department of Education, Employment and Workplace Relations, 2008) and recognized as key elements to providing good practice in values-based education:

- 1. Establish and consistently use a common and shared values language across the school;*
- 2. Use pedagogies that are values-focused and student-centered within all curriculum;*
- 3. Develop values-based education as an integrated curriculum concept, rather than as a program, and event or an addition to curriculum;*
- 4. Explicitly teach values so students know what the values mean and how the values are lived;*

5. *Implicitly model values and explicitly foster the modeling of values;*
6. *Develop relevant and engaging values approaches connected to local and global contexts and which offer real opportunity for student agency;*
7. *Use values-based education to consciously foster intercultural understanding, social cohesion and social inclusion;*
8. *Provide teachers with informed, sustained and targeted professional learning and foster their professional collaborations;*
9. *Encourage teachers to take risks in their approaches to values-based education; and*
10. *Gather and monitor data for continuous improvement in values-based education.*

V.E.G.P.S.P. - Stage2 provided a continued exploration of values based educational programs in Australian schools. The action research methodology was based on a plan, do, study, act, cycle that enabled schools and clusters to respond flexibly to project needs (Australian Government: Department of Education, Employment and Workplace Relations, 2008). Student Action Teams (S.A.T.s), Values Action Teams (V.A.T.s) and student peer support initiatives formed the student focused pedagogy with groups of students identifying and tackling school and community issues. Both in Stages 1 & 2 of the Final Report, case study findings were consistent in what ingredients they described as being advantageous for the successful implementation of values-based education in Australian school curricula.

Australian Schools School Cluster Case Studies: Values-based Education Implementation (2)

Case 5: A Summary of the Information and Communication Technologies Approach Experiences of Two Cluster Groups.

A key development from Stage 2 cluster project work was the implementation of information and communication technologies (I.C.T.) not only as an educational tool to build student knowledge about values but also for social networking to explore and enact values by way of intranet Q&A forums, blogging, etc. (Australian Government: Department of Education, Employment and Workplace Relations, 2008). The Unity in Diversity Cluster (N.S.W.) focused on improving respect for individual identities and respect for other cultures. This cluster was

geographically located in a region south of Sydney called Cronulla, infamously known for the 2005 Cronulla race riots. This cluster's mix of schools included Islam faith based and state schools. The five schools established a collaborative website, that is, an intranet site, and students were able to visit each other online and use this virtual space to discuss impressions of project activities that took place and other issues that interested them. The website, in its capacity as a communicative tool, encouraged students to challenge stereotypes that were presented in the main media (Australian Government: Department of Education, Employment and Workplace Relations, 2008).

The Cross Borders Cluster, consisting of schools in the Northern Territory, South Australia and Western Australia, was a unique cluster group consisting 8 geographically remote schools across two states and one territory which focused on the National Framework value, fair go, defined in Appendix 3 – Australian Values for Australian Schools poster. This cluster group brought teachers together to engage in P.D. online in real-time and brought students together to participate in the study of environmental education values dilemmas, again online and in real-time. *Centra*, a distance communication system, was used to offer real-time web-based learning to the schools and this software created virtual classrooms in which teachers could share their expertise and students could overcome their isolation and gain exposure to new perspectives. During these online sessions, the students discussed various topics in values-based education, for example, exploring the values embedded in local environmental projects. Each of these cluster schools conducted their own mini-projects which were relevant to their own needs and student interests, for example, removing noxious weed species and planting native reeds at a local lake (Lewis, Mansfield & Baudains, 2008). A particularly interesting point of this cluster's project work was the inclusion of an online moderator of student online interactions, that is, a teacher, who guided online discussions and then challenged students with dilemma oriented concepts to enrich their understanding of fairness (Australian Government: Department of Education, Employment and Workplace Relations, 2008). In 2008, the Final Report of the Values Education Good Practices Schools Project - Stage 2, concluded that values education can be incorporated into school curriculums successfully, noting that a number of cluster project outcomes in Stage 2 (following up on the practices demonstrated in Stage 1),

“clearly suggest that the most effective learning experiences in values education are generally values

explicit, student centered and open ended... (demonstrated) successful pedagogies engage students in real-life learning, opportunity for real practice and provide safe structures for taking risks, and encourage personal reflection and action.”

Teacher Efficacy, Staff Leadership and Values-based Education

The Australian Commonwealth government aimed to support teachers in their participation of the teaching and learning of values-based education in Australian schools through the N.F.V.E.A.S.'s (2005) Section A: School Planning – in which values-based education was regarded as an explicit goal of school planning and Section F: Quality Teaching – in which it was recognized that teachers needed to be skilled in the best practices of teaching values-based education and that they needed to be provided with appropriate resources to support their efficacy as teachers of values within all areas of the curriculum and total school life and that this efficacy needed to be monitored on an ongoing basis. As Lickona notes in Milson (2001), values-based education is far more complex than teaching math or reading, it requires personal growth as well as skills development. Furthermore, Milson (2001) argues that teacher efficacy beliefs are a combination of personal influence and perceptions of the influence of factors external to the classroom. In Milson's (2001) U.S. based investigative report of teacher efficacy in relation to values-based education, over 1,800 elementary and secondary school teachers from Mid-western school districts participated and significant findings were produced. Teacher responses indicated that teachers have positive attitudes toward character education. Using a 5 point answer key (SA = strong agree / A = agree / U = uncertain / D = disagree / SD = strongly disagree) teacher responses, scored as collective percentage answers, were as follows and the findings were significant to teacher efficacy in values-based education:

- 1. Teachers who spend little time encouraging students to be respectful of others will see little change in students' social interaction. (90.8% agreed or strongly agreed);*
- 2. Teachers are usually not responsible when a child becomes more courteous. (89.1% disagreed or strongly disagreed);*
- 3. I am usually comfortable discussing issues of right and wrong with my students. (96.8% agreed or strongly agreed);*
- 4. I am confident in my ability to be a good role model. (99.2% agreed or strongly agreed);*
- 5. I am usually at a loss as to how to help a student be more responsible. (92.8% disagreed*

or strongly disagreed);

6. *Teachers who encourage responsibility at school can influence student's level of responsibility outside of school. (88.3% agreed or strongly agreed);*
7. *If parents notice that their children are more responsible, it is likely because teachers have fostered this trait at school. (57% agreed or strongly agreed); and*
8. *Some students will not become more respectful even if they have had teachers who promote respect. (70.2% agreed or strongly agreed);*

Teacher self-efficacy is related to democratic classroom style teaching and learning practices when cooperation among students is promoted, that is, through the employment of discussion, decision making, problem solving and conflict resolution which can lead to not only academic development but also ethical skill development (Narvaez, Vaydich, Turner, & Khmelkov, 2008). O'Sullivan (in Mergler, 2008) after examining the reasons for school teachers in Australia entering their profession found that they desired to make a difference to the lives of students and to help them to become more aware of their needs, abilities and goals and that they desired to shape, support and care for students. Additional reasons for entering the teaching profession included the desire to help young people and make a positive contribution to society. If these are indeed legitimately influential reasons for school teachers entering their profession, then teaching teachers to explore the values they believe and the choices and behavior they express equips them with skills to better teach these same skills to their future students.

Quality Teaching and Values-based Education: a Double Helix Effect on Learning

In their comprehensive study on the affect that quality teaching has on student achievement, Lovat & Clement (2008b) advocated that a quality teaching regime must provide conditions of teaching and learning where teachers and students are actively, critically and reflectively involved in knowledge-making and personal human growth. These two researchers argue that values-based education has become an inextricable part of all school teaching and learning due to the need to discover new ways to deal with persistent problems of racism, drug abuse, domestic violence, sexual abuse, AIDS and new terrorism inspired by the most explicit values based beliefs (Lovat & Clement, 2008b). In 1994, the Taskforce for Learning in the

Primary Grades, funded by the Carnegie Corporation of New York embarked upon an extensive study of the effects of effective learning in primary level schooling. A member of this task force, Linda Darling-Hammond, performing research about the role of the teacher in effective teaching and learning, reported that student achievement is less predicted by teacher salaries, levels of expenditure, and class size than by a teacher's subject and pedagogical knowledge, and quality teaching (Lovat & Toomey, 2007).

Furthering the belief in the inextricable relationship between teacher quality and student achievement, the Carnegie Learning Report (1994) advocated that the role of the teacher goes beyond surface learning, that is, factual acceptance and memorization of information, standardized testing, etc.; this role requires engaging students in skills commonly referred to by educationalists as communicative capacity and self-reflection. Communicative capacity is derived from the self-reflective practitioner recognizing that their life as being part of and functioning within a large number of worlds and in order to possess communicative capacity they develop, as communicative actors, with other people and with ideas that extend beyond their own world. Halliday, in Lovat & Clement (2008b), postulates that teaching is a moral activity and calls for teachers to maintain authenticity in their teaching by way of constant moral reflection. Cawsey, in Lovat & Clement (2008b, p. 6), succinctly notes the argument for quality teaching, stating that:

“There is considerable anecdotal evidence that accomplished teachers recognize that the deepest levels of learning occur at the level of values, at the point where a student takes his/her learning and makes personal meaning from it. Without that connection at the values level, students can master the technical aspects of the curriculum but will be unlikely to value the learning experience or the school that provided it.”

Thus, the development and maintenance of positive relationships and the reduction of cultural and social divides between teachers and students should be a priority of quality teaching and learning in schools.

Lovat & Toomey (2007), in their study of the relationship between quality teaching and values-based education, identified key skills that students exhibit in the optimal circumstances of receiving quality teaching:

- ***Intellectual depth*** – *perceptiveness, intuition, and the capacity for analysis and evaluation;*

- **Communicative capacity** – the ability to talk with others about the process of exploring the values, how the students engaged with the process, what outcomes flowed from it, what they learned and what it means to practice the values;
- **Empathic character** – demonstrating a sensitivity and compassion for the world around them, within and beyond their immediate environment;
- **Capacity to reflect** – the ability to think back to an event or some other act, consider the impact it had and plan how things might be done better;
- **Self-management** – the ability to work with others and with oneself around issues related to values and ultimately, to live out these values;
- **Self-knowledge** – knowing oneself better and becoming better more comfortable with oneself, thereby gaining more poise in the learning process.

The double helix diagram, in Appendix 11, depicts the interconnectedness and flowing nature between values-based education and quality teaching. Lovat and Toomey (2007) argue for the teaching of values to be explicit, well transmitted and central to teaching and a school curriculum, noting that when teachers and students are consciously trying to be respectful, honest, tolerant, and doing their best, then the dynamic of the classroom changes. The outcome of which is that teacher satisfaction grows and student concentration improves.

Self-reflection and Educational Leadership

An Australian based study by Branson (2007) explored the question of authentic leadership and values development. Authentic leadership implies that leaders are aware of their own values and that they are true to these personal values, possessing self-knowledge and personal points of view that reflect clarity about their values and convictions, enabling them to analyze and review their own motivations and underlying values in order to confirm or amend them as valid guides for actions (Branson, 2007). Branson's research in this 2007 report focused on a study of the concept of authentic leadership with seven Catholic primary school principals in Brisbane, Australia. From this research, Branson (2007) recognized that for people to effectively understand and clarify personal values they require guidance in knowing what to look for in their Self, that is, the integration of one's own self-concept, self-esteem, motives, values, beliefs, and behaviors. Hence, the clarification of values, rather than being a natural process of learning, does

involve a deep sense of one's Self and the ability to self-reflect. Branson (2007) utilized a deep-structured approach to self-reflection, based on the theoretical premise that values are indirectly linked to behaviors through beliefs, to assist the school principals in their realizing that the way they behaved influenced their educational leadership and leadership behavior.

By understanding their inner Self, each principal was able to discern their leadership behavior more effectively and this was particularly evident when a principal inappropriately applied values, negatively affecting their leadership behavior by weakening the positive effects of their actions within the school community. An example of this case in point follows (Branson, 2007, p. 12):

“Principal A was able to recognize that his struggle to cope with group and committee meetings resulted from his strong commitment to valuing independence...by knowing the origins of this value empowered him to begin to redress this weakness in his leadership by using affirming techniques towards other group members whenever he became aware that he was waning in his commitment to the group or committee activity.”

Accounts from the other eight principals showed equally productive results, making a strong case for deeply structured self-reflection as a process that can enhance authentic leadership practices among school administrators and teachers by clarifying thinking, raising self-awareness and developing better professional relationships within school communities.

Beyond Teacher Efficacy: Teachers Working in Partnership with Parents and Families

A 2002 study undertaken by Andrew Mullins, an Australian school principal, investigated the preparedness of beginning teachers to work in partnership with parents in academic and character building areas. The study presented observations made by 35 independent school principals across Australia and noted strong implications for teacher education concerning their partnerships with students' parents, namely:

- 1. Teachers need to foster in the eyes of the children the esteem of their parents;*
- 2. Schools need to foster unity with parents in every aspect of school life;*
- 3. Schools should support parents and not challenge parental values and build the understanding that schools are a service to parents;*
- 4. Schools need to deliver clear and open communication with parents and increase teacher-parent personal communication; and*

5. *Schools need to be consistent with character education messages to students, that is, teaching what is right and wrong and show the reasons.*

Ryan and Bohlin (in Mullins, 2001) contend that while parents are the child's primary character educators, teachers and schools are major players. From the viewpoint of parents, they need to know what is going on in their child's school life and from the side of the teachers, they need to know that feel that the parents are supportive of their role as lead educators of character in the classroom. Brannon (2008, p. 59) pointedly contends that children develop:

“much of their identity and beliefs about right and wrong before entering school...if character education is strongly enforced at school but not at home (or vice versa), students are confused about what (if any) rules to follow.”

Thus, it is very evident that schools and parents need to work together to develop students' character and the findings of V.E.G.P.S.P.: Stages 1 & 2 additionally support this contention.

Values-based Education Support Resources (Précis)

The main exploration of this paper has been concerned with values-based education programs in Australian schools. Recognition of the abundantly accessible resources to aid the formulation, implementation and evaluation of values-based education programs has been provided so far in this paper. However, there are numerous organizations that provide further information about values-based education for educators and the general public. Cited from the worldwide web, a list and précis of several useful websites particularly relevant in the primary school aged educational context of teaching and learning is noted in this section, although if fully detailed the list web based resources for values-based education, in Australia alone, would be very lengthy:

- **The Australian Council of State School Organisations (A.C.S.S.O.)** is the peak national organization representing the interests of the parents, families and schools communities of more than 2 million children attending government schools throughout Australia. It has membership networks in all States and Territories. A.C.S.S.O. recognizes that all schools should always seek to improve what they do and find out what values the families in their communities want them to promote (www.acsso.org.au);
- **Principals Australia (P.A.)** is a non-for-profit incorporated body owned by the four peak Australian principals associations, representing secondary and primary Government,

Catholic and Independent sectors. P.A. exists to support principals and their associations to build effective, inspirational, and sustainable leadership in Australian schools, particularly on the learning and well-being of students (www.pa.edu.au);

- **Civics and Citizenship Education (C.C.E.)** is an Australian Commonwealth Government web portal that promotes civics and citizenship education. Its main focus is on supporting students' participation in Australia's democracy, including developing knowledge and understanding of Australia's democratic heritage and traditions, its political and legal institutions and to share values of freedom, tolerance, respect, responsibility and inclusion. It has a wide range of resources available to teachers, students and parents (www.civicsandcitizeneducation.edu.au); and
- **Living Values Education (Australia)** is the Australian Associate of an international association of independent, locally run, non-profit organization (funded in part by the United Nations) committed to promoting values-based education. Its objectives, holistic in nature, include: helping individuals to think about different values and the practical implications of expressing them in relation to themselves, others, the community, and the world at large; and to encourage educators and caregivers to look at education as providing students with a philosophy of living for facilitating their growth, development and choices of behavior so that students can integrate themselves into the community with respect, confidence and purpose (www.livingvalues.net).

Conclusion

Australian Government implementation of a values-based education program in all Australian schools over the past decade has been successfully carried out through the support of a school grants program and the support of all state and territory governments, regardless of the ideologies of their elected leaders. Shaw (2009, p. 10) notes that:

“For many schools, the National Framework for Values Education in Australian Schools (2005) and supporting materials provided direction for values to be constructively discussed in terms of school improvement and quality teaching and learning. Aligning values, purposes and practice has become a focus for many school communities.”

In 2008, as a keynote speaker at the National Education Values Forum in Canberra, Australia, Andrew Furco, an American educationalist who is well recognized for his research into service learning, delivered a comprehensive presentation about the future of values-based education and his key observations are congruent with the findings of the aforementioned and discussed outcomes of the National Frameworks for Values Education in Australian Schools in promoting the employment of the following conditions for successful values-based education (Australian government: Department of Education, Employment and Workplace Relations, 2008):

- *maintain high quality practices;*
- *support professional development;*
- *focus on the purpose rather than the program;*
- *find educational priorities on which to hook values-based education;*
- *connect to the global agenda; and*
- *be patient.*

As a keynote speaker at the National Education Values Forum (2006), British educationalist, Neil Hawkes shared his belief in the importance of conversations between one generation and another about matters of significance, such as, values, and praised Australia’s success with values-based education in schooling in this respect by noting the country as a world leader in values-based education (Australian government: Department of Education, Employment and Workplace Relations, 2008). High praise and recognition from international observers and home-grown policy success shows that indeed values-based education is an integral part of

school education in Australia. Arguably, the conversation between one generation and the next in Australia is heading in a healthy and productive direction.

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Appendices

Appendix 1. Kohlberg's Levels of Moral Development

SOURCE: KOHLBERG, (1963,1981)

Kohlberg's Levels of Moral Development

LEVEL	STAGE	CHARACTERISTICS OF STAGE/LEVEL
A Preconventional	Stage 1	PUNISHMENT-OBEDIENCE ORIENTATION
	Stage 2	INSTRUMENTAL RELATIVIST ORIENTATION
B Conventional	Stage 3	INTERPERSONAL CONCORDANCE ORIENTATION
	Stage 4	AUTHORITY AND SOCIAL-ORDER MAINTAINING ORIENTATION
C Postconventional Autonomous, or Principled	Stage 5	SOCIAL-CONTRACT LEGALISTIC ORIENTATION
	Stage 6	UNIVERSAL ETHICAL PRINCIPLE ORIENTATION

Source: Huitt, W. (2004). Values. *Educational Psychology Interactive*

Appendix 2. Values-based Education Approaches

Overview of Typology of Values-based Education Approaches		
Approach	Purpose	Methods
Inculcation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To instill or internalize certain values in students; To change the values of students so they more nearly reflect certain desired values 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Modeling; Positive and negative reinforcement; Manipulating alternatives; Games and simulations; Role playing
Moral Development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To help students develop more complex moral reasoning patterns based on a higher set of values; To urge students to discuss the reasons for their value choices and positions, not merely to share with others, but to foster change in the stages of reasoning of students 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Moral dilemma episodes with small-group discussion; Relatively structured and argumentative without necessarily coming to a "right" answer
Analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To help students use logical thinking and scientific investigation to decide value issues and questions To help students use rational, analytical processes in interrelating and conceptualizing their values 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Structured rational discussion that demands application of reasons as well as evidence; Testing principles; Analyzing analogous cases; Research and debate
Values Clarification	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To help students become aware of and identify their own values and those of others; To help students communicate openly and honestly with others about their values; To help students use both rational thinking and emotional awareness to examine their personal feelings, values, and behavior patterns 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Role-playing games; Simulations; Contrived or real value-laden situations; In-depth self-analysis exercises; Sensitivity activities; Out-of-class activities; Small group discussions
Action Learning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Those purposes listed for analysis and values clarification; To provide students with opportunities for personal and social action based on their values; To encourage students to view themselves as personal-social interactive beings, not fully autonomous, but members of a community or social system 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Methods listed for analysis and values clarification; Projects within school and community practice; Skill practice in group organizing and interpersonal relations

Source: Huitt, W. (2004). Values. *Educational Psychology Interactive*

Appendix 3. Nine Values for Australian Schooling Poster – National Framework for Values Education in Australian Schools

Source: Australian Government: Department of Education, Employment and Workplace Relations (2005)

Appendix 4. National Framework for Values Education in Australian Schools

Key Elements	Suggested Approaches
A. School planning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Values-based education is an explicit goal of school planning. • School values are made explicit with the assistance of the school community. • Values objective are made clear in the planning strategies and introduced to students at an appropriate learning stage with clearly defined outcomes identified. • Regular reviewing of values-based education practices against the identified outcomes is built into school planning processes.
B. Partnerships within the school community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Schools consult parents, caregivers and families within their communities on values to be fostered and approaches to be adopted (e.g. through school values forums). • Values-based education involves the local school community in the development and teaching of values drawing on the shared values that underpin Australia's democratic way of life in the context of the local community and its values. • Schools involve the community in the implementation and monitoring of values-based education programmes.
C. Whole school approach	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Schools apply their values-based education priorities to their overall curriculum provision, their structures and policies, their procedures and rules, their funding priorities, their decision making arrangements, their disciplinary procedures, their community relations and their welfare/pastoral care approaches.
D. Safe and supportive learning environment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Schools provide a positive climate within and beyond the classroom to help develop student's social and civic skills and build student resilience and responsibility and to ensure a safe and supportive environment for values-based education. • Students, staff and parents are encouraged to explore their own values. • Values-based education supports good practice pedagogy and is introduced in the curriculum at appropriate times for learners.
E. Support for students	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Schools develop programmes and strategies to empower students to participate in a positive school culture and to develop their local, national and global responsibility. • Schools use values-based education to improve student social skills and resilience. This includes addressing issues such as behavior management and discipline, violence and bullying, substance abuse and other risk behavior, disconnectedness and alienation, student health and well-being, improved relationships and students' personal achievement.
F. Quality teaching	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Teachers are skilled in good practice values-based education. • Teachers are provided with appropriate resources to support their efficacy as teachers of values within all areas of the curriculum and total school life and to monitor this efficacy on an ongoing basis. • Schools and educational leaders recognise that values interact with and are integral to all key learning areas.

Source: Australian Government: Department of Education, Employment and Workplace Relations (2008)

Appendix 5. The Value of Doing Your Best (exemplified by a cluster)

As a student I can show I am doing my best by:

Attending all my classes in time/arriving at school on time.

Trying really hard all the time.

Persisting

Being involved in extra activities like sporting competitions or dance festivals

Setting a goal and working to achieve it

Listening

Handing in my homework/assignments on time

Not letting myself get distracted

As a teacher I can encourage my students to do their best by:

Rewarding positive behavior/celebrating achievement

Reflecting on my own practice and modeling a commitment to self-improvement

Providing opportunities for students to succeed in school and in the wider community

Expecting excellence and giving students the chance to take a risk in their learning

Communicating openly with parents and students

As a parent/carer I can encourage my child/ren to do their best by:

Celebrating their achievements

Encouraging them to set goals in their learning

Encouraging them to be positive about school and learning

Source: Australian Government: Department of Education, Employment and Workplace Relations (2006)

Appendix 6: Sample Lesson for Social Skills Approach

Focus

Positive and negative social behaviors – Creating a board game to demonstrate and share understanding

Values demonstrated

Fair Go; Respect; Responsibility; Understanding; Tolerance and Inclusion; Integrity

Learning outcomes

Throughout the lesson, students will be working towards demonstrating:

1. their understanding of socially appropriate behaviors;
2. their ability to work cooperatively and responsibly;
3. an understanding of their role in the school community.

Activities

Check in – The thing I most enjoy about school is ...

Mixer – Use a technique of your choice to divide students into groups of four to six.

Central Activity – Explain to students that they will be making a Social Behaviors Board Game which will then be used by students in Year 7 to learn about social behaviors. They may like to make it a snakes and ladders style game or come up with their own format. Moves will need to target positive and negative social behaviors. They first will need to make a list of what these behaviors might be (e.g. responsible/irresponsible; cooperative/uncooperative). Then they can begin to design their games. They will have this and the next lesson to complete this, so will need to allocate roles within their groups to ensure that everything can get done.

Check out – A positive social behavior/a negative social behavior we are including is ...

Resources

Cardboard, color pens, pencils, scrap paper for brainstorming and drafting.

Source: Australian Government: Department of Education, Employment and Workplace Relations (2006)

Appendix 7. Concept Development - Thinking Skills

Year level	Teaching sequence for inquiry skills	Thinking tools; concept development activities	Question techniques
Year 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> *questioning *building on ideas of others *reasons *giving examples 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Suggestions Reasons 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> What is it that puzzles you? What did you find interesting? Is someone puzzled by something in the story?
Year 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> *agendas *seeking and giving clarification *connections *explanations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Agreement/disagreement Examples – bridge 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Why did you say that? What reasons do you have? Why do you agree or disagree with...? Have we some reason to think that...?
Year 3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> *different points of view *descriptions *definitions *analogies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Borderline cases Target Thought experiments Thumbs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Would that be a good reason for believing that...? Does anyone have a different reason? Does anyone have a better reason? How certain can we be that...? Is it like...said? It sounds like you agree/disagree with...? Is that right?

Source: Australian Government: Department of Education, Employment and Workplace Relations (2006)

Appendix 8. Values Social Literacy Units

Schooling level	Inquiry Based Learning Units	Focus KLAs	Values
Lower Primary (1,2 & 3)	<p>FRIENDS What makes a good friend?</p> <p>WIPE OUT WASTE How can we make our school beautiful?</p>	<p>SOSE/HPE/ Arts</p> <p>Science/SOSE</p>	<p>Care and Compassion, Responsibility & Honesty</p> <p>Responsibility</p>
Middle Primary (4,5)	<p>WATER WISE What does it mean to be water wise?</p> <p>WHO MADE AUSTRALIA GREAT?</p> <p>GOING, GOING, GONE Do animals have rights? Can we protect our animals before it is too late? What can we do to make a difference?</p>	<p>Science</p> <p>SOSE</p> <p>SOSE/Science</p>	<p>Respect, Responsibility</p> <p>Doing Your Best</p> <p>Respect, Responsibility</p>
Senior Primary (6,7)	<p>FACES OF AUSTRALIA What do you value about cultural diversity?</p> <p>VALUED POSSESSIONS What do you value and why?</p> <p>BEING AUSTRALIAN Who are we and where do we come from?</p>	<p>SOSE/HPE</p> <p>English</p> <p>SOSE</p>	<p>Understanding, Tolerance & Inclusion</p> <p>Freedom, Doing Your Best,</p> <p>Respect, Understanding, Tolerance & Inclusion</p>

Source: Australian Government: Department of Education, Employment and Workplace Relations (2006).

Appendix 9. Social Action on What it means to be Water Wise (Year 4 & 5)

Stage of Inquiry	Focus Questions	Teaching/learning episodes	Assessment
<p><u>Taking social action</u></p> <p>*Undertake social project that applies new understanding</p> <p>*Create product/text</p> <p>*Present/share</p>	<p>*What resources will I need to undertake this action?</p> <p>*What assistance will I need?</p> <p>*What difficulties might I have?</p> <p>*Next week/lesson I need to...</p> <p>*Are all group members doing their fair share?</p> <p>*Have I done my bit?</p>	<p><u>Water Wise Expo:</u></p> <p>*Negotiate range of activities/displays that will be included in the expo. Aim to include samples of work taken during the term.</p> <p>*Establish timelines and student responsibilities.</p> <p>*Encourage students to take different roles: meet and greet invitations, advertisements, signage, catering, speakers, photographer, management of each display, performers.</p> <p><u>Group Reflections:</u></p> <p>*See list of focus questions</p>	<p><u>Participation:</u></p> <p>*Individual & group work</p> <p><u>Letter writing</u></p>

Source: Australian Government: Department of Education, Employment and Workplace Relations (2006)

Appendix 10. Red Earth Community Cluster Value Focus for Good Citizenship

Respect for others

Showing care for others, especially their feelings

Using manners and “magic” words – being courteous

Listening when others are talking – showing interest

Including other people in what you do

Accepting people’s differences – race, beliefs, cultures, opinions...

Showing that being different is ok

Showing tolerance

Following rules and laws

Respect for yourself

Believing in yourself

Keeping yourself healthy by eating healthy food and exercising

Being positive about yourself and others

Respect for property

Taking care of your own and other people’s belongings

Asking before you use something that isn’t yours

Respect for the environment

Taking care of the environment - not littering or vandalizing

Reducing greenhouse gases by walking not driving

Above all – Treat others the way you want to be treated.

Source: Australian Government: Department of Education, Employment and Workplace Relations (2008)

Appendix 11. The Double Helix Effect: Values and Quality Teaching

Source: Lovat, T. & Toomey, R. (2007) *Values education and quality teaching: The double helix effect*. Sydney: David Barlow Publishing

Appendix 12. Cumulative Occurrence of Values-based Education Discourses in the Values-based Education Good Practices School Trial 2006 (selected discourses)

Source: Jones, T. M. (2009). Framing the framework: discourses in Australia's national values education policy

Appendix 13. Y-chart and Placemat Worksheets

Source: Kiernan, J. (2005). *Values Education in Australian Schools: support materials for Tasmanian Schools*

Appendix 14. Pluses, Minuses and Interesting Points Worksheet

Focus:

Plus	Minus	Interesting

Comments: _____

Source: Kiernan, J. (2005). *Values Education in Australian Schools: support materials for Tasmanian Schools*

Appendix 15. K-W-L Strategy Worksheet

Topic:

What I KNOW ?	What I WANT to Know?	What I have LEARNED ?

Source: Kiernan, J. (2005). *Values Education in Australian Schools: support materials for Tasmanian Schools*

Appendix 16. Venn diagram for a Social Action Project

Source: Australian Government: Department of Education, Employment and Workplace Relations (2006)